

Using augmented reality in hydropower plant management and maintenance

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Abstract

The hydropower plants are increasingly constructed and managed on a building information modelling (BIM) platform and operations are getting automated for better performance. With the energy market getting competitive due to the technological advancements in the solar and wind power sector, even the ageing power plants are also upgraded with the latest technologies to maintain their competitiveness as cheap and clean energy. But the maintenance and inspection are still carried out manually using the conventional method of using paper-based manuals, 2D drawings and specifications.

Therefore, Augmented reality (AR) is one of the promising technologies for cognitive assistance in a complex working environment that requires manual input. The thesis focuses on the potential of AR technologies for the maintenance and inspection of power plants. It highlights the requirement and challenges to implement AR in power plants with and without 3D BIM models as the methodology is different.

The AR can facilitate the operators to better understand the task to be performed or the condition of the components by displaying the virtual information such as instructions, faulty components, analysed data and other relevant information superimposed with the real object/scene. The information can be presented in a structured way for better comprehension which would improve performance.

The introduction of new technologies to the workplace would face initial reluctance and challenges to train the workforce. The benefits would be noticed when the users are conversant with the technology.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

https://youtu.be/Am3hL5gf_Ys

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